

PROPAGATION PREDICTIONS FOR MARGINAL LOS MICROWAVE PATHS

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes a mathematical algorithm and an associated program set developed for calculating time distributions of the effective earth-radius factor, k , for marginal line-of-sight (LOS) paths. The algorithm is a modification of a procedure developed for use in the continental United States by J. A. Schiavone at Bell Laboratories. From the distribution of k , we obtain the profile geometries applicable to various fractions of a year and from the geometries, median basic transmission loss values and antenna pointing losses are calculated. The method is useful because military LOS paths are often long and are designed with limited terminal site options.

Schiavone's model depends upon values for a number of climatological parameters. This paper lists sources and describes methods for estimating these values and provides an alternative method for mathematically expressing the refractivity distribution.

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this paper is to describe an algorithm and program set used to predict the performance of line-of-sight (LOS) paths for which the clearance of the antenna beam above obstacles is marginal. Since the algorithm is long, we describe only the first three steps of the performance prediction procedure. An example of their application is provided.

Diffraction fading on LOS links has usually been treated by specifying that antenna heights be great enough to prevent the occurrence of such fading. The heights were selected on the basis of antenna-beam center clearance calculated using an extreme earth-radius factor (often 2/3) and a first-Fresnel-zone-radius clearance factor (often 0.3 or 0.6). There are problems with this approach: first, tactical applications often preclude the use of high antennas; and second, this approach is costly because some paths require less clearance than others since the clearance requirement depends upon climatological factors. An alternative to a fixed-extreme-earth-radius-factor approach for establishing antenna heights in the continental United States is provided by

Schiavone [1] and Vigants [2]. In the present work, this approach has been modified to make it applicable to the long, marginal LOS paths used by the U.S. Military organizations in other parts of the world. Important advantages of this approach are a) that it may be applied where conditions do not permit the use of high antennas, and b) that the effect of obstacle diffraction on performance can be predicted. Diffraction fading tends to occur on LOS paths when the atmosphere is stratified and atmospheric refractivity increases with height near the surface. Such a mechanism bends the radio beam upward, which has the approximately equivalent effect of keeping the atmosphere heterogeneous and decreasing the earth's radius. The bending of the antenna beam also depoints the antennas.

The path analysis is based on a time distribution of effective-earth-radius-factor, k , where k is the ratio of the effective earth radius to the true earth radius. The distribution of k is derived from a distribution of refractivity gradient estimates in the lower atmosphere. Only distributions of gradients that are nearly constant (at a given elevation) over substantial areas of land are of interest. The Schiavone method of analysis provides this type of distribution. Gradient data have long been available at discrete points but when extrapolated over long paths, the resulting path predictions were unreliable. The Schiavone model requires values for a number of climatological parameters. Sources for and methods of estimating these values are presented. An alternative method for mathematically expressing the refractivity gradient distribution estimate is also presented which provides the user with some flexibility in matching the form of distributions measured for various parts of the world.

MODEL AND PROGRAM SET DESCRIPTION

The performance of marginal LOS paths can be predicted by running the "Performance of mixed-mode microwave paths" (POMMP) program set which is written in HPL programming language and which was prepared by the Institute for Telecommunication Sciences for the U.S. Army Electronic Systems Engineering Installation Activity, Ft. Huachuca, AZ. The "POMMP" program set functions as follows:

19.3.1

1. Schiavone's methods are used to obtain expressions for the two normal cumulative probability distributions of refractivity gradient, G, representing the stratified and mixed atmosphere regimes.

2. From these two normal distributions, a cumulative bimodal distribution of G is synthesized that represents all parts of the annual distribution where the refractivity gradient is not strongly negative.

3. From the distribution of refractivity gradients, a cumulative distribution of effective-earth-radius factors is obtained.

4. Based on a range of effective-earth-radius-factors, a set of path profile and ray path geometries is calculated from which is obtained a cumulative distribution of signal loss due to obstacle diffraction [2, pp. 791-792] and antenna depointing.

5. The signal loss distributions due to obstacle diffraction, rain attenuation, and multipath are processed with information about the diversity configuration and the radio equipment to obtain a cumulative time distribution of carrier-to-noise ratio.

6. The distribution of carrier-to-noise ratio is then processed with the single-receiver transfer function to predict the performance of the radio path.

This paper considers the process of predicting performance only through step 3 (the distribution of k).

DISTRIBUTIONS FOR THE TWO REGIMES

The first step in the procedure (obtaining an expression for each of the two normal distributions) may be described in the following way. Each of the two normal distributions represents different atmospheric conditions. For small percentages of time, the distribution representing a stratified lower atmosphere is the most important. The other distribution represents a mixed atmosphere, which dominates most of the time. If we work with a normal-to-linear transformation of the cumulative probability axis, the distributions may be represented by the equations for two straight lines. These equations are:

$$G_m = S_{dm} X_p + G_{mm} \quad (1)$$

$$G_s = S_{ds} X_p + G_{sm} \quad (2)$$

where the variables are defined as follows:

- G_m = gradient distribution for the mixed regime.
- S_{dm} = standard deviation for the mixed regime.
- G_{mm} = intercept value for the mixed regime.
- G_s = gradient distribution for the stratified regime.
- S_{ds} = standard deviation for the stratified regime.
- G_{sm} = intercept value for the stratified regime.

- X_p = inverse cumulative normal probability function. It is used as the normal-to-linear variable transformation function of cumulative probability, p.
- p = probability that the corresponding refractivity gradient value is not exceeded.

Values for these variables are found as follows:

S_{dm} = 15 N-units per km per standard deviation [1, p.813].

G_{mm} = median refractivity gradient [3].

$G_{sm} = G_{mm}$

X_p = approximate values obtained from the function x_p from reference 4. If p is less than or equal to 0.5, $X_p = -x_p$. If p is greater than 0.5, $X_p = x_{1-p}$.

$$S_{ds} = (1400/L_t^{1/4})(f_t H_h)^{1/2} (D_c f_c V_w M_c)^{1/4} \quad (3)$$

For inland regions:

$$S_{ds} = (1400/L_t^{1/4})(f_t H_h)^{1/2} (a_i V_w M_i)^{1/4} \quad (4)$$

An inland region is one where the radio path is more than 300 km from a large body of water (one with an area greater than 40,000 square km).

The variables used in the expressions for S_{ds} are defined as follows:

- L_t = lower atmosphere layer thickness (meters).
- f_t = probability of occurrence of temperature inversions.
- H_h = horizontal homogeneity of stratified air.
- D_c = water proximity factor.
- f_c = favorable (to stratification) wind direction occurrence factor.
- V_w = water vapor capacity.
- M_c = modification factor for coastal regions based on moisture index.
- a_i = 4.7×10^{-5} (an empirically determined constant).
- M_i = modification factor for interior regions based on moisture index.

For elaboration on these variables, see Schiavone's discussion [1]. Values for these variables are obtained or estimated as follows:

- L_t = Lower atmosphere layer thickness. It generally ranges between 50 and 500 m. A layer thickness of 150 m is typical.
- f_t = values for probability of occurrence of temperature inversions. These values are available for the continental United States [5, p.322]. The range of values for the United States is between 0.05 and 0.5. This range is probably valid for the rest of the world with possible exception of the polar regions. Morita provides a rough map of the world showing areas having frequent temperature inversions [6].

H_h = value of horizontal homogeneity of stratified air. It ranges between 0.14 and 1. For over-water paths and very smooth terrain, $H_h = 1$. The value of H_h is based on the roughness of the terrain in the general vicinity of the path. For areas outside the continental United States, an approximate value may be obtained from the expression:

$$H_h = H_1 \times H_2 \quad (5)$$

where $H_1 = 1 - 0.03 \ln [\exp(S_1 - 20) + 1] + 0.03 \ln [\exp(S_1 - 40) + 1]$ (6)

S_1 = standard deviation of terrain elevations with the antenna sites and the area near them excluded.

and $H_2 = 1 - 0.0025 \ln [\exp(H_{ME} - 200) + 1] + 0.0025 \ln [\exp(H_{ME} - 400) + 1]$ (7)

H_{ME} = mean terrain elevation with data from the antenna sites and the area near them excluded.

The equations for H_1 and H_2 are the results of efforts by the authors to obtain values for these variables from terrain elevation statistics which are close to the values obtained by Schiavone using topographic map classifications. Outside the continental United States, we assign his H_3 a value of 1.

D_C = water proximity factor value. It is obtained from the expression:

$$D_C = [1 + (d_w/300)^4]^{-1} \quad (8)$$

d_w = minimum distance in km from either of the sites or the path to a large body of water such as an ocean, gulf, or great lake. The value of d_w is positive and less than 300 km.

f_C = favorable wind direction occurrence factor, which has a value between 0 and 1. Because of the subjectivity required for picking this value, a default value is estimated to be 0.25. The map from reference 7 may be of some help in selecting a value for f_C more objectively.

V_w = value for water vapor capacity. It is estimated using the expression:

$$V_w = \{\exp[21.71 - 5433/(T_a + 273.18)]\}/50 \quad (9)$$

T_a = average temperature in degrees Celsius [7]

M_C = modification factor for coastal regions. It is based on the moisture index, m_x . This index was developed by Thornwaite [8, opposite p. 94], who provides a map of m_x values for the United States. Based on this map, an expression for estimating m_x was derived. The value for M_C is given by the equation:

$$M_C = 20/(70 + m_x) \quad (10)$$

For areas outside the continental United States, an estimate of m_x is given by the expression:

$$m_x = -2.3 T_a + 0.067 M_r \quad (11)$$

where T_a = average temperature in degrees Celsius [7].

and M_r = average annual rainfall in millimeters [7].

$a_i = 4.7 \times 10^{-5}$, an empirically determined constant [1, p. 811].

M_i = modification factor for interior regions. It is also based on the moisture index, m_x . The value for M_i is given by the expression:

$$M_i = m_x + 100 \quad (12)$$

FORMING THE BIMODAL DISTRIBUTION

Schiavone forms the bimodal distribution by first estimating the fraction of time (0.8) that the radio path is under the mixed regime and the fraction of time (0.2) that it is under the stratified regime. The time that gradients are strongly negative is not included in the distribution. The seasonally averaged density functions for the mixed and stratified regimes are multiplied by their corresponding occurrence fractions. The probability density functions are then integrated over his variable N' to give the bimodal distribution.

The method recommended here produces much the same distribution but permits the user to conveniently adjust the shape of the distribution to conform more closely to distribution curve shapes suggested by data [9]. The adjustments of parameters m_B , k_1 , and X_1 in equation 15 provide this flexibility. To describe the method, we first describe the process for using the constants from the equations for two straight lines to produce a single function approximating parts of both lines using their slopes and the coordinates of their intersection. Assume equations for the two straight lines as follows:

$$Y_A = m_A X + b_A \quad (13)$$

$$Y_B = m_B X + b_B \quad (14)$$

A function, Y_C , which approximates parts of both lines (figure 1), has the form:

$$Y_C = m_A X + b_A + [(m_B - m_A)/k_1] \log_b [b^{k_1(X - X_1)} + 1] \quad (15)$$

where X_1 = the "X" value of the intersection of the two straight lines

and k_1 = any positive number whose magnitude controls the radius of curvature near the intersection point.

Figure 1. Combining portions of linear functions.

Additional log terms can be used to represent portions of other line segments to synthesize more complex functions.

Using this method, an expression for the bimodal distribution may be obtained based on the following assumptions:

1. For the 90 percent of values representing the largest refractivity gradients, the bimodal distribution has the same general shape ($k_1 = 1$, $b = 10$, and X_p at the intersection = -1.3) as the Cocoa Beach refractivity distributions [9, p.49] except that the standard deviation of the part of the bimodal distribution dominated by the stratified regime varies according to climatological values as stated in equations 3 and 4. To calculate the intersection value, X_i , used in the bimodal distribution equation (16), we proceed as follows. Two points (defined by $p = 0.002$ and $p = 0.02$) on each of the four Cocoa Beach curves are used to define a line through the annual median which has a slope of -15 n-units/km/standard deviation. The negative of the average of these four X_p intersection values is equal to X_i .

2. Let $-X_p = X$, $S_{dm} = m_A$, $G_{mm} = b_A$, $S_{ds} = m_B$, $k_1 = 1$, $b = 10$, and $-X_p$ at the intersection = X_i .

The bimodal distribution is given by the following expression:

$$G = -15 X_p + G_{mm} + (S_{ds} - 15) \log \left[10^{\frac{-(X_p + 1.3)}{k_1}} + 1 \right] \quad (16)$$

where G = the refractivity gradient value not exceeded for the corresponding value of X_p and therefore the corresponding fraction of time, p .

The POMMP programs always use the intersection value, -1.3 , but for some parts of the world the user may desire to change the program to reflect other intersection values [9, p.59].

Figure 2. Example predicted gradient distribution.

An example of a cumulative distribution of G is shown in Figure 2.

CONVERTING REFRACTIVITY GRADIENT TO "k" FACTORS

To convert the cumulative time distribution of the refractivity gradient, G , into a distribution of the earth's radius factor, k , we use an approximate expression from Dougherty [10] which is:

$$k = [1 + 6370 G \times 10^{-6}]^{-1} \quad (17)$$

where 6370 km represents the earth's actual radius.

APPLICATION EXAMPLE

This analysis of a marginal LOS path is based on the algorithms previously described and the "POMMP" program set. Accuracy of the analysis is very dependent upon the accuracy of:

- 1) Antenna elevations above mean sea level
- 2) Obstruction elevation above mean sea level
- 3) Calculated refractivity gradient distribution.

The probability that temperature inversions will occur is important in calculating this refractivity gradient distribution. It is a strong variable in the expression for the stratified regime standard deviation. Since there is little accurate information available in published literature on the probability of temperature inversions in the vicinity of this path, we have selected a conservative value (0.2) which is lower than values observed in most parts of the United States.

Figure 3 shows the effects of positive refractivity gradients on the effective-earth-radius path profile for 0.1 , 0.01 , and 0.001 fractions of a year. Table 1 shows estimated amounts of attenuation from several causes, and in this case it shows the dominant role of obstacle diffraction (including antenna depointing) in producing outage time on this path. Note that the

Figure 3. Effect of "k" distribution on path geometry.

attenuation values caused by multipath are large but that this type of attenuation is substantially overcome through the use of either space or frequency diversity. Diversity is not helpful in reducing the other types of atmospheric fading.

Figure 3 and Table 1 show that the path clearance is adequate 9 tenths of the time. Table 1 shows that for 0.01 of the time (about 90 hours per year) the beam is partially blocked, which would cause an additional path loss of 11 dB or more during these hours. The table also shows a large blockage for about 9 hours per year with diffraction losses greater than 40 dB. Of this amount, about 5 dB is due to depointing (for a 5-m diameter antenna). From this example, it becomes apparent that obstacle diffraction and depointing should not be neglected in the design of marginal line-of-sight paths.

One of the weakest parts of this performance prediction process is the selection of a suitable value for probability of temperature inversions. An effort should be made to produce contour maps showing expected values for this parameter in areas of the world in which the U.S. military organizations have particular interest.

Table 1. Attenuation Exceeded for Various Numbers of Hours per Year Due to Multipath, Rain-Rate, and Obstacle Diffraction Fading

Fraction of Average Year	Time (Hours per Year)	Multipath Atten. (dB)	Rain Atten. (dB)	Obstacle Diffraction (dB)
0.1	900	---	0	0
0.01	90	21.5	3.6	11.7
0.001	9	31.5	11.5	39.8
0.0001	0.9	41.5	22.2	61.9

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